

Space-Time Outlier Identification in a Large Ground Deformation Dataset

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Abstract

A novel application for outlier detection is in ground deformation monitoring. During any type of underground construction in urban settings, sensors are placed on the ground surface to monitor the vertical displacement with the goal of ensuring that there is no substantial heaving or settling of the ground. As a result, a large spatial-temporal dataset is produced, but the sensors are often very sensitive, and spurious readings are commonly observed, resulting in both random and systematic outliers. In this work, we present a novel, fast spatial-temporal quality control procedure that is designed to remove these spurious readings prior to subsequent ground deformation monitoring. First, a robust kriging model is applied to the spatial ground deformations at each time point to remove systematic errors; and next, an exponential moving average model is applied to the time series of ground deformations at each station to remove random outliers. A case study using ground deformation data when four subway tunnels are bored under a rail yard in Queens, New York is used to illustrate the methodology. Methods used to construct outlier bounds are described, and the accuracy of an outlier detection approach is evaluated by calculating the percentages of outliers detected in an introduced artificial outlier set.

Some keywords: Big Data; Outlier Detection; Spatial-Temporal

Short title: Space-Time Outlier Identification

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1 Introduction

Monitoring processes with spatial and/or temporal structure arise commonly in environmental problems, such as atmospheric pollution (Bobbia et al. 2015; Harrou et al. 2016; Fasso et al. 2007) or temperature (Shaby and Reich 2012). Such monitoring problems also arise in engineering applications, such as wafer design (Wang et al. 2014), material manufacturing (Miller and Forbes 2009; Miller et al. 2012), or ground deformation (Mooney et al. 2015). Prior to monitoring, it is important to remove any spurious observations from the dataset. Two types of errors often appear in a spatial-temporal dataset. *Systematic errors* can arise from instrument calibration, new instrumentation, undocumented changes in station location, or changes in units of measure. They often appear as repeated errors that persistent over a longer timeframe. *Random errors* can arise from incorrect data entry and transmission, electronic noise, instrument failure, or sensor resolution (Anderson et al, 2015; Sun et al, 2017). They show no pattern and are inconsistent with observations in the surrounding spatial neighborhood, temporal neighborhood, or spatial-temporal neighborhood, but they are not necessarily gross outliers. A random outlier may well be within a global range of values, but it could be very different locally from the observations around it in space or time.

As noted in Bobbia et al. (2015), many outlier detection methods have been designed to handle multivariate data (e.g., Chandola, et al. 2009; Filzmoser et al. 2005; Filzmoser et al. 2008; and Filzmoser et al. 2014), but fewer have been introduced to explicitly account for spatial or spatial-temporal structure. However, some recent work is beginning to appear in this area. Sun and Genton (2012) use adjusted functional boxplots for exploratory space-time outlier detection. Cerioli and Riani (1999), Wang et al. (2014), and Bobbia et al. (2015) use kriging to capture spatial structure in data.

In Bobbia et al. (2015), the concentrations of atmospheric pollutant PM_{10} in a region in France are studied, and two spatial outlier detection methods are developed and compared. In one approach, they use a nearest neighbors weighted median method, similar to Lu et

49 al. (2003), but ultimately, the results from the kriging approach are more promising, and
 50 we build upon their work for spatial outlier detection but now in a space-time context. The
 51 classical approach to spatial outlier detection (e.g., Rousseeuw and Leroy 2005; Bobbia et
 52 al. 2015) is to compute residuals based on a spatial prediction at the location of interest
 53 without using that location’s value to make the prediction, namely

$$R_t^{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{s}_j) = Z_t(\mathbf{s}_j) - \hat{Z}_t^{(-j),\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{s}_j), \quad (1)$$

54 where $Z_t(\mathbf{s}_j)$ is the value of the observation at time t and location \mathbf{s}_j , and $\hat{Z}_t^{(-j),\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{s}_j)$ is
 55 its predicted value, computed using model \mathcal{M} and without observation \mathbf{s}_j . Using historical
 56 residuals, upper and lower bounds are constructed, and if $R_t^{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{s}_j)$ falls outside of these
 57 bounds, then the observation is flagged. However, if more than one observation lies outside
 58 of these bounds at time t , Bobbia et al. (2015) then remove the largest such observation
 59 (in absolute value) and recompute the predicted values, $\hat{Z}_t^{(-j),\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{s}_j)$, with this observation
 60 removed. This process is repeated until all remaining observations lie within the bounds.

61 While this method certainly takes advantage of the spatial dependence in the process,
 62 and the bounds are location specific and are allowed to vary over time, some improvements
 63 can be made. First, the quality of the residuals are highly dependent on the model, \mathcal{M} ,
 64 used to make the predictions. Evaluating the quality of a proposed model in the presence
 65 of outliers can be difficult, and we propose a more robust measure of model fit to assess
 66 the fitted model prior to using it to construct residuals. Secondly, Bobbia et al. (2015) use
 67 the R package `geoR` (Riberio and Diggle 2001) to estimate the parameters of an exponential
 68 semi-variogram to describe the spatial dependence and subsequently use this spatial model to
 69 make spatial kriging predictions with the R package `gstat` (Pebesma 2004). The exponential
 70 model is often a good choice in practice to model spatial dependence, and we use the same
 71 model, but no further details are given about how the model is fit. If they took the common
 72 approach of computing the classical semi-variogram estimator as proposed by Matheron

73 (1962), it is strongly influenced by outliers, so we use a robust kriging approach to produce
74 spatial predictions based on work by Künsch et al. (2011). Finally, the iterative method
75 that Bobbia et al. (2015) use to recompute the residuals each time an outlier is removed is
76 computationally intense, so using robust spatial predictions eliminates this costly step.

77 Furthermore, good predictions are not guaranteed simply by obtaining a robust semi-
78 variogram estimator. The prediction process is still affected by the existence of extreme
79 values in the data. To illustrate, assume that $z_t(\mathbf{s}_j)$ is the only outlier in a dataset. The
80 predicted value $\hat{z}_t^{(-j)}(\mathbf{s}_j)$ is not affected by the outlier $z_t(\mathbf{s}_j)$ because it is not used, and all the
81 other observations used for obtaining $z_t(\mathbf{s}_j)$ are in the normal range. But when predicting
82 at another location $z_t(\mathbf{s}_i)$ where \mathbf{s}_i is a location close to \mathbf{s}_j , the fact that $z_t(\mathbf{s}_j)$ is an outlier
83 affects the prediction of $z_t(\mathbf{s}_i)$. The result is that the prediction of every observation in the
84 neighborhood of an outlier is affected, which greatly disturbs the calculation of residuals and
85 damages the ability to use residuals in outlier detection, no matter how scarce those the
86 outliers are. For this reason, using robust kriging is even more important.

87 Finally, we differentiate between detecting systematic outliers and random outliers in a
88 spatial-temporal dataset. First, we compare three different modeling approaches for detect-
89 ing systematic outliers—a non-robust spatial model, a robust isotropic spatial model, and
90 a robust anisotropic spatial model. Next, we compare four different modeling approaches
91 for detecting random outliers—purely temporal, purely spatial, temporal then spatial, and
92 spatial then temporal. The residuals from each modeling approach computed within a rolling
93 window are used to continually update the upper and lower bounds beyond which observa-
94 tions are flagged, so the process is allowed to evolve dynamically over time. We also compare
95 parametric and nonparametric approaches to selecting the upper and lower bounds. By in-
96 troducing artificial systematic and random outliers into the ground deformation dataset, we
97 can directly assess the ability of the methods to correctly detect outliers and can gain insight
98 into the types of outliers that spatial versus temporal models can identify.

99 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: in Section 2, we describe the problem
100 of ground deformation monitoring and the dataset. Section 3 presents both the systematic
101 and random outlier detection methodologies that we use and propose. Section 4 describes the
102 results of these methods as applied to the ground deformation data, and then we conclude
103 with a discussion of a recommended method and future work in Section 5.

104 2 Data Description

105 In 2011 and 2012, a project was undertaken in Queens, New York where four shallow tun-
106 nels for subway lines were excavated beneath an active railway yard in soft ground (soil).
107 Figure 1 shows a map of the region, rail lines, and tunnels. The rail yard was operated
108 continuously during the tunneling, and thus close monitoring of the surface was required to
109 ensure smooth operations. Ground deformation data, specifically vertical surface displace-
110 ment, was collected via manual surveying of many locations using tripod-mounted total sta-
111 tion and human recording, as well as automated surveying of many locations using robotic
112 or automated total stations (AMTS). The manual surveying and AMTS measurements are
113 described in Mooney et al. (2015). Manual surveying is difficult to collect at a high tem-
114 poral frequency due to the activities of the rail yard, but the AMTS measurements, which
115 were placed throughout the rail yard, were able to observe the ground deformation every 2.4
116 hours (or ten times daily). Furthermore, manual measurements contains more error, both
117 systematic and random, than AMTS data. For each station, we analyze 1,580 equally-spaced
118 time series AMTS observations recorded from December 1st, 2011 to May 7th, 2012, when
119 tunnel excavation took place. We have 371 monitoring points recorded by AMTS stations
120 that are also shown in Figure 1 and would have 586,180 total observations if the dataset were
121 complete, but given missing values, the dataset contains a total of 323,806 observations.

122 While the AMTS data is high frequency in time, it is susceptible to a variety of errors.
123 Many of the AMTS monitoring points are located along the rail lines or on infrastructure

124 that need monitoring. As a result, systematic errors, in which a large upward or downward
125 shift is applied to all observations after a given point in time, can occur when the monitoring
126 sensor is moved by a train or environmental conditions. Random errors are those in which
127 a single observation in time or space is very different from its neighbors, and these occur
128 due to electrical noise, transmission errors, or when measurements are on the order of the
129 sensor resolution, which is often the case. Figure 2 shows an example of each of these types
130 of errors along with shaded colored regions that show when each of the four tunnels is within
131 50 meters of the monitoring station. Both stations show periods of missing observations, and
132 this is very common across all stations. Note that the deformations are given in millimeters
133 (mm) and remain at a value of zero when no movement occurs.

134 Ultimately, this data would be used to alert the operators of the tunnel boring machines if
135 an unacceptable level of surface deformation is occurring, and in response, they would adapt
136 or modify their operations. Both review and alert levels (15 mm and 38 mm, respectively, for
137 the rail lines according to Mooney et al. (2015)) are set *a priori* based on what is considered
138 allowable for the infrastructure. However, prior to developing a method for identifying spatial
139 regions in which the review or alert levels are exceeded with high probability, the erroneous
140 observations should be discarded, and this process should be a fast, pre-processing step.

141 **3 Methods**

142 In this section, we first describe an improved approach for detecting systematic outliers by
143 using spatial models that are robust in the presence of outliers. A robust measure of the
144 predictive ability of spatial models is also described. Second, we discuss the methods for
145 detecting random outliers by using temporal models, spatial models, and a combination
146 of spatial and temporal models. We construct outlier bounds beyond which to classify
147 an observation as an outlier. The methods are illustrated throughout with the ground
148 deformation data.

149 3.1 Systematic outlier detection

150 In ground deformation data, the systematic outliers refer to stations producing observations
 151 that are repeatedly inconsistent with other stations in the spatial neighborhood. We detect
 152 systematic outliers by flagging outlying stations in space at each time point. Assuming
 153 $\{Z_t(\mathbf{s}_1), \dots, Z_t(\mathbf{s}_n)\}^T$ is a realization of the random field $\{Z(\mathbf{s}) \in \mathbb{R}^d\}$ at time t where
 154 $d \geq 1$, and $Z_t(\mathbf{s}_j)$ is the deformation at location \mathbf{s}_j for $j = 1, \dots, n$ and $t = 1, \dots, k$,
 155 a spatial model can be constructed based on the spatial structure observed in the data
 156 and knowledge of the data-generating process. The residuals of a spatial model \mathcal{M} are
 157 calculated using Equation (1). Spatial outliers are detected by constructing outlier bounds
 158 using $\{R_t^{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{s}_j)\}_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq t \leq k}$, where n is the number of spatial stations and k is the number
 159 of time points. An observation $Z_t(\mathbf{s}_j)$ is considered an outlier if the residual $R_t^{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{s}_j)$ falls
 160 outside of the corresponding outlier bound.

161 As mentioned in Section 1, robust kriging is necessary when outliers are present in spatial
 162 data. Instead of using the two step approach of robustly estimating the empirical semi-
 163 variogram (with, for example, the estimator presented in Genton, 1998) and then estimating
 164 the spatial model parameters using weighted least squares (Cressie 1985) with which to do
 165 kriging, robust prediction is needed for every location in the spatial domain when even one
 166 outlier is present. Simply removing outliers is not appropriate for small data sets and is
 167 cumbersome for large ones, so a method that simultaneously robustly estimates the semi-
 168 variogram model parameters and robustly predicts $Z_t(\mathbf{s}_j)$ at every location is crucial. Künsch
 169 et al. (2011) propose a novel method for a robust restricted maximum likelihood (REML)
 170 estimation of the external drift and the variogram of a Gaussian random field contaminated
 171 by outliers, together with robust kriging prediction. We briefly sketch their method.

Assume the model \mathcal{M} is $Y(\mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{s})\boldsymbol{\beta} + Z(\mathbf{s}) + \varepsilon(\mathbf{s})$ where $\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{s})\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the external drift,
 $Z(\mathbf{s})$ is a stationary Gaussian random field with zero mean and covariance $R(\mathbf{h}; \sigma_0^2, \alpha)$, and
 $\varepsilon(\mathbf{s}) \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ is the nugget effect. Here, $\mathbf{h} = \|\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}'\|$ is the Euclidean distance between

location \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{s}' . Let $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\sigma_0^2, \alpha)^T$ in which σ_0^2 is the sill and α is the range. Gaussian maximum likelihood (ML) or REML can be used for model estimation. The log-likelihood of \mathcal{M} can be written as

$$\ell(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \sigma^2, \boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{y}) = -\frac{1}{2} \log[\det(\sigma^2 \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{V}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}})] - \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})^T (\sigma^2 \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{V}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}})^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}),$$

172 where $\mathbf{V}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is the covariance matrix of the random field. Let $\mathbf{z} = [z(\mathbf{s}_1), \dots, z(\mathbf{s}_n)]^T$ be the
 173 unobserved value of the random field, and then the pseudo-likelihood is

$$\ell^*(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \sigma^2, \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{z} | \mathbf{y}) = -\frac{1}{2} \log[\det(\sigma^2 \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{V}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}})] - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{y(\mathbf{s}_i) - \mathbf{x}(\mathbf{s}_i)^T \boldsymbol{\beta} - z(\mathbf{s}_i)}{\sigma} \right]^2 - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{z}^T \mathbf{V}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \mathbf{z}. \quad (2)$$

174 Setting partial derivatives of Equation (2) with respect to each parameter and \mathbf{z} to zero, we
 175 can get parameter estimates and predicted values of \mathbf{z} at any location. A problem with this
 176 method is that both the estimation of model parameters and the prediction of \mathbf{z} depend on
 177 the standardized residuals $\hat{\mathbf{r}}/\hat{\sigma} = (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \hat{\mathbf{z}})/\hat{\sigma}$, which is sensitive to outliers in \mathbf{y} . Künsch
 178 et al. (2011) adopted a procedure suggested by Welsh and Richardson (1997) to replace $\hat{\mathbf{r}}/\hat{\sigma}$
 179 by the bounded and odd function

$$\psi_c(x) = \frac{2c}{1 + \exp(-2x/c)} - c,$$

180 in which a positive value c is a tuning parameter controlling the robustness of the estimates.
 181 We see that $\lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} \psi_c(x) = \pm c$, so the smaller the value c is, the more robust the estimates
 182 and predicted values are. The robust estimates are obtained by using a method combining
 183 an iteratively re-weighted least squares (IRWLS) approach and a Broyden's scheme. The
 184 method is implemented in R package `georob` (Papritz and Schwierz, 2016).

185 Mooney et al. (2015) mention that temperature may have an impact on ground defor-
 186 mation with higher temperature causing the rail tracks to expand and the ground to heave.

187 We investigated this possible association but found no significant influence on ground defor-
188 mation. There was also no significant association between longitude or latitude and ground
189 deformation, so we use ordinary kriging and can eliminate the external drift term, $\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{s})\boldsymbol{\beta}$,
190 from the above formulation.

191 Thus, to obtain robust predictions, we use the Künsch et al. (2011) method to build a
192 robust kriging model in a leave-one-out approach for the spatial data observed at each time
193 point. At time t , for the data $\{Z_t(\mathbf{s}_1), \dots, Z_t(\mathbf{s}_n)\}^T$, we build a kriging model by using all
194 the observations except that at location \mathbf{s}_i and use this model to obtain the robust predicted
195 value $Z_t^{(-i)}(\mathbf{s}_i)$ for $Z_t(\mathbf{s}_i)$. This process is repeated for every station with a non-missing value
196 at time t and all $t = 1, \dots, k$.

197 Many of the ATMS ground deformation stations are located on the rail tracks, which
198 run in a nearly straight line at an approximately 75 degree direction from the north. For
199 this reason, we assume that the deformation of monitoring points close to each other in the
200 direction of the rail tracks behave similarly, and therefore, anisotropic models are likely to
201 produce better predictions than isotropic models. The type of anisotropy displayed in the
202 ground deformation data is geometric anisotropy, in which the data in different directions
203 show different values of the sill, but the range is the same (see Journel and Huijbregts (1978),
204 section III.B.4 for more detail on anisotropic models). Geometric anisotropy can be handled
205 by rotating and shrinking the coordinate system to reduce the directional effect, and then
206 we use an isotropic spatial model on the transformed coordinates to estimate parameters
207 and make spatial predictions.

208 Figure 3 shows a typical empirical omni-directional semi-variogram compared with the
209 directional semi-variogram for two sets of angles for ground deformation at time 2012-03-09
210 00:00:00 EST. The semi-variogram for $(68, 88]$, which is parallel to the tracks, contains aver-
211 ages of squared differences in ground deformation for pairs of observations within this angular
212 range of each other, and similar computations are made for pairs of observations within the

213 range of angles $(-92, 68]$, which is perpendicular to the tracks, The omni-directional semi-
 214 variogram does not show spatial dependence. From the directional semi-variogram, we see
 215 that the association for observations in the parallel track direction is stronger at short dis-
 216 tances apart. On the other hand, the association for observations perpendicular to each
 217 other is weaker at short distances.

218 3.2 Robust model assessment

219 To quantitatively compare the prediction accuracy of a spatial model \mathcal{M} , we introduce a
 220 spatial prediction index (SPI), computed in the following steps:

- 221 1. Calculate $\delta_j = [Z(s_j) - \hat{Z}^{(-j), \mathcal{M}}(s_j)]^2$ for $j = 1, \dots, n$ from Equation (1).
- 222 2. Calculate the $100(1 - \alpha)$ th quantile of $(\delta_1, \dots, \delta_n)$ as $\delta(\alpha)$. Define $\mathcal{K} = \{j : \delta_j < \delta(\alpha)\}$.
- 223 3. Calculate

$$\text{SPI}(\alpha) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} [Z(s_j) - \hat{Z}^{(-j), \mathcal{M}}(s_j)]^2}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} [Z(s_j) - \bar{Z}_\alpha(s_\bullet)]^2},$$

224 in which $\bar{Z}_\alpha(s_\bullet)$ is the trimmed mean of $Z(s_j)$ for $j \in \mathcal{K}$, and α is a value we choose
 225 to control the robustness.

226 $\text{SPI}(\alpha)$ can be used to robustly measure the prediction accuracy of a model, \mathcal{M} , relative to
 227 predicting with the trimmed mean based on those observations with residuals below $\delta(\alpha)$.

228 For the ground deformation data, we fit the non-robust kriging model (NR), the robust
 229 isotropic kriging model (ISO), and the robust anisotropic kriging model (ANISO) for the
 230 spatial data at each of 1,580 time points. The leave-one-out approach is used to do kriging
 231 prediction. For each kriging model, we use the exponential model to fit the empirical semi-
 232 variogram. Figure 4 shows the boxplot of $\text{SPI}(0.05)$ for the three types of kriging models. The
 233 mean and median of $\text{SPI}(0.05)$ for the three models (NR, ISO, ANISO) over all time points
 234 are $(0.11, 0.43, 0.51)$ and $(-0.01, 0.44, 0.52)$, respectively. On average, the anisotropic kriging

235 model explains over 50% of the variation in the squared residuals with respect to the trimmed
236 mean, so it performs the best among the three. The value of $\text{SPI}(0.05)$ of the isotropic kriging
237 models is slightly lower than that of the anisotropic models, demonstrating the benefit of
238 including a directional effect in the spatial dependence of the ground deformations. Because
239 there are many outliers in the data, the non-robust model fails to capture the spatial structure
240 and produces an $\text{SPI}(0.05)$ of nearly zero at 60% of the time points, and the average $\text{SPI}(0.05)$
241 is also only 0.11. Figure 5 shows the observed and predicted ground deformation for stations
242 at two time points using three different kriging models. At time point 2012-04-04 14:24:00,
243 an outlier with value 0.953 at station 637 inflates the prediction of a nearby station up to
244 0.642, which is much larger than the predicted values at other stations. At time point 2011-
245 12-23 19:12:00, a few large negative outliers cause disturbance in the predictions of nearby
246 stations. The result is that by using non-robust kriging models, many observations in the
247 normal range may be flagged as outliers if they are close to a station with spatial outliers.
248 Figure 6 illustrates this concept for station 707 and its closest spatial neighbor, station 706.

249 **3.3 Random outlier detection**

250 In the ground deformation data, random outliers refer to observations that are inconsistent
251 with other observations in their spatial and temporal neighborhood. We can compare purely
252 temporal, purely spatial, and a combination of temporal and spatial approaches to identify
253 them. Here, we describe each of these approaches.

254 *Temporal modeling approach*

255 A temporal model can be used to explain the variation in values observed over time at every
256 station. Because long periods of missing data frequently appear, a simple, nonparametric
257 modeling approach is preferred. We use the exponential moving average model (MA) to fit
258 the observations at each station. Given a time series $\{Z_t(\mathbf{s}_i)\}_{t=1}^k$ observed at station \mathbf{s}_i , the

259 predicted value for $Z_t(\mathbf{s}_i)$, denoted $\hat{Z}_t(\mathbf{s}_i)$, is

$$\hat{Z}_t(\mathbf{s}_i) = \beta \hat{Z}_{t-1}(\mathbf{s}_i) + (1 - \beta)Z_t(\mathbf{s}_i),$$

260 which is a linear combination of the prior time point's prediction and the current observed
261 value. Here, $\beta \in (0, 1)$ and determines the decay effect of the past observations on the
262 prediction of the current value. For the ground deformation data, we get good prediction by
263 setting $\beta = (n_E - 1)/(n_E + 1)$, where n_E is the number of observations to average over, and
264 we set it be 10. When computing the exponential moving average, we skip all time points
265 with missing data. The residuals from the MA model's predictions for each station are
266 then used to construct residual bounds for outlier detection. Note, the MA model produces
267 predictions, not forecasts forward in time.

268 *Spatial modeling approach*

269 Spatial models can be fit for data at each time point if spatial dependence exists. We use the
270 robust anisotropic kriging model (RS) discussed in Section 3.1 for the ground deformation
271 data to compare it with other modeling approaches in detecting random outliers.

272 *Spatial and temporal modeling approaches*

273 If we use the MA model to fit the ground deformation data, the residuals from the MA model
274 may still contain spatial dependence. Similarly, the residuals from the RS model may still
275 also contain temporal dependence. Therefore, combining the MA model and RS model may
276 assist in identifying more outliers. This can be done in two ways. First, fit the MA model
277 for the original ground deformation values for each station to remove temporal outliers, and
278 then fit the RS model to the residuals of the MA model with outliers removed. The outliers
279 detected from MA models and those detected from the subsequent RS models are considered
280 to be the outliers in the ground deformation data. Or, we may reverse the process to fit the
281 RS model first and then the MA model, with outliers flagged and removed at both stages.

282 3.4 Outlier bound construction

283 **Rolling Windows:** After we obtain the residuals from the temporal models or spatial
284 models for all spatial-temporal locations with valid observations, the next step is to construct
285 outlier bounds. Depending on whether the spatial field is homogeneous or not, we could pool
286 residuals across stations to build one outlier bound at each time point, or take residuals at
287 each station across all the time points to form separate outlier bounds for each station.
288 Bobbia et al. (2015) assumed that the concentrations of PM₁₀ in Normandy, France were
289 not spatially homogenous, and this was reasonable given that monitoring stations were near
290 differently sized cities. Thus, they constructed a different set of outlier bounds for each
291 monitoring station by using only historical data from that station.

292 As mentioned before, the spatial data at each time point is more heterogenous than the
293 temporal data at each station in the ground deformation dataset, so constructing separate
294 residual bounds for each monitoring station is reasonable. But considering that (a) working
295 on the the MA models largely reduces the variation across stations, and (b) pooling the
296 residuals across stations for each time point would enable us to implement our method in
297 real projects for identifying random outliers in a timely manner, we construct temporal
298 outlier bounds that apply to all stations at that time rather than create a separate outlier
299 bound for each station. For detecting systematic outliers, we think it is necessary to pool
300 residuals across stations since isolating residuals for a single station over time will fail to
301 detect systematic outliers for that station.

302 For the residuals $\{R_t(\mathbf{s}_j)\}_{1 \leq t \leq k, 1 \leq j \leq n}$, outlier bounds are constructed by creating rolling
303 windows $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{k-d+1}$ across time. Window w_1 contains the residuals from time point
304 1 to time point d for all stations, so $w_1 = \{R_t(\mathbf{s}_j)\}_{1 \leq t \leq d, 1 \leq j \leq n}$. Window w_2 contains the
305 residuals from time point 2 to time point $d+1$ for all stations, so $w_2 = \{R_t(\mathbf{s}_j)\}_{2 \leq t \leq d+1, 1 \leq j \leq n}$.
306 Other windows are created similarly. All of the windows are fixed at length d , which is chosen
307 to ensure there are enough non-missing observations in each window to quickly construct

308 stable and useful outlier bounds. The residuals in each window are used to construct the
 309 outlier bounds to detect outliers in the spatial observations at the time point right after the
 310 window. For example, the window w_1 is used to construct outlier bound B_1 , and B_1 is used
 311 to detect outliers at time t_{d+1} . B_2 is used to detect outliers at time t_{d+2} and so on. We set
 312 $d = 30$, which is enough observations in each window to construct stable outlier bounds.

313 **Threshold Construction:** Both parametric and nonparametric thresholds can be used as
 314 outlier bounds for each window. For the parametric threshold, we calculate the sample mean
 315 $\hat{\mu}_i$ and sample standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}_i$ of all of the residuals in window w_i . The outlier bound
 316 for window w_i is denoted as $B_i = (L_i, U_i)$ where $L_i = \hat{\mu}_i - \Delta\hat{\sigma}_i$ is the lower bound, and
 317 $U_i = \hat{\mu}_i + \Delta\hat{\sigma}_i$ is the upper bound. The value of Δ can be selected to be between 2.5 and
 318 4, depending on how conservative we want the outlier bound to be. For the nonparametric
 319 threshold, we calculate the $100(\alpha/2)$ th quantile as the lower bound L_i and the $100(1-\alpha/2)$ th
 320 quantile as the upper bound U_i of the residuals in window w_i . Common values of α chosen
 321 are between 0.01 and 0.05.

322 Figure 7 shows the value of the nonparametric and parametric outlier bound for each time
 323 point for the robust spatial anisotropic kriging (RS) model, and the two types of bounds at
 324 each time point for the moving average (MA) model. We set $\alpha = 0.02$ for the nonparametric
 325 bounds and set $\Delta = 3$ for the parametric bounds. For the RS model, the parametric outlier
 326 bounds are symmetric and more stable than the nonparametric bounds, and they produce
 327 better results in detecting systematic outliers (See Section 4). For the MA model, the two
 328 types of outlier bounds look similar, and they produce similar results in detecting random
 329 outliers.

330 4 Case Study

331 In this section, we describe how we introduce artificial systematic and random outliers into
 332 the ground deformation dataset, and then we quantitatively measure the performance of the

333 outlier detection methods proposed in Section 3 by calculating the proportion of introduced
334 outliers detected by each method.

335 4.1 Introducing Artificial Outliers

336 To introduce random outliers to the ground deformation dataset, we randomly select 3,185
337 (1%) of all valid spatial-temporal locations, and for each selected location, we change the
338 ground deformation to a value that would be considered an outlier in that location’s spatial-
339 temporal neighborhood. A spatial-temporal neighborhood of an observation $z(\mathbf{s}_0, t_0)$ can
340 be defined as $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{s}_0, t_0) = \{z(\mathbf{s}_{0(1)}, t_{0(1)}), \dots, z(\mathbf{s}_{0(1)}, t_{0(k_1)}), \dots, z(\mathbf{s}_{0(k_2)}, t_{0(k_1)})\}$, in which
341 $z(\mathbf{s}_{0(k_2)}, t_{0(k_1)})$ is the k_1^{th} nearest observation from $z(\mathbf{s}_{0(k_2)}, t_0)$ in time, and k_2^{th} nearest ob-
342 servation from $z(\mathbf{s}_0, t_{0(k_1)})$ in space. Given that spatial variation is stronger than temporal
343 variation in the ground deformation data, we set $k_1 = 30$ and $k_2 = 8$. With this set-
344 ting, each spatial-temporal neighborhood contains 240 observations. For a value $z(\mathbf{s}_0, t_0)$
345 that we want to change to an outlier, we calculate the 25th quantile Q_1 , the 75th quan-
346 tile Q_3 , and the inter-quantile range $IQR = Q_3 - Q_1$ of the observations in $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{s}_0, t_0)$,
347 then change $z(\mathbf{s}_0, t_0)$ to a random value generated from a uniform distribution with support
348 $(Q_1 - d_2 \cdot IQR, Q_1 - d_1 \cdot IQR) \cup (Q_3 + d_1 \cdot IQR, Q_3 + d_2 \cdot IQR)$, in which we set $d_1 = 1.5$
349 and $d_2 = 3$.

350 To introduce systematic outliers, we randomly select 20 out of 371 stations and add a
351 constant to one third of the consecutive observations at each selected station. For each
352 station, the constant shift value is randomly selected from $(-1, -0.5) \cup (0.5, 1)$. In this way,
353 we get 7,446 (2.3%) introduced systematic outliers in total. Examples of stations with both
354 introduced systematic and random outliers are shown in Figure 8.

355 4.2 Systematic Outliers

356 Table 1 summarizes the number of detected and undetected systematic outliers among the
357 set of introduced outliers. In addition, the number of outliers from the original ground de-
358 formation data (excluding observations that are changed to artificial outliers) are reported.
359 Results from both parametric outlier bounds and nonparametric outlier bounds are given.
360 The number in the parentheses is the percentage of artificially introduced outliers that are
361 successfully detected or are not detected by the corresponding modeling approach and thresh-
362 old setting. We set α to be 0.02, 0.03, and 0.04 for the nonparametric outlier bounds, and
363 set Δ to be 4, 3, and 2.5 for the parametric outlier bounds, so the outlier detection results
364 are comparable between the two types of bounds.

365 As expected, when we increase α or decrease Δ , the number of detected systematic
366 outliers increases in both the artificial outlier set and the original ground deformation data.
367 The robust isotropic kriging model detects more outliers in the artificial outlier set and fewer
368 outliers in the original ground deformation data compared to non-robust kriging model.
369 As discussed in Section 3, outliers inflate the prediction of ground deformation at nearby
370 stations; therefore, the non-robust kriging model produces more false positives and fewer true
371 positives. The robust anisotropic kriging model improves the outlier detection compared
372 to the robust isotropic model in the ground deformation data by further increasing the
373 true positives and decreasing false positives. The parametric outlier bounds perform better
374 than the nonparametric outlier bounds in outlier detection, by detecting more outliers in
375 the introduced outlier set and detecting fewer outliers in the original outlier set. As an
376 example, the parametric outlier bounds detect 6,946 (93%) of the outliers in the artificial
377 outlier set with the anisotropic model with $\Delta = 2.5$, compared with 6,255 (84%) with the
378 nonparametric outlier bounds. Furthermore, the number of detected outliers in the original
379 ground deformation data is 4,846 for the parameter outlier bounds, much lower than the
380 6,605 detected by the nonparametric outlier bounds. The same results are observed for

381 other models and threshold settings.

382 **4.3 Random Outliers**

383 Table 2 summarizes the random outlier detection results using the following four modeling
384 approaches: (a) the exponential moving average (MA); (b) the robust spatial anisotropic
385 kriging model (RS); (c) the MA model followed by RS model, with outliers removed after
386 the first stage (MA-RS), and (d) the RS model followed by the MA model, with outliers
387 removed after the first stage (RS-MA).

388 We observe from Table 2 that MA models perform uniformly better than RS models
389 in detecting random outliers. Comparing the two-by-two sub-tables for MA models and RS
390 models in Table 2 for any value of α or Δ , we see the MA models detect more random outliers
391 in the artificial random outlier set and fewer outliers from the original ground deformation
392 data. RS models do poorly in detecting random outliers because in the ground deformation
393 data, the temporal data at each station is much more homogenous than the spatial data at
394 each time point. MA models can explain most of the variation in the data to successfully
395 detect random outliers. Secondly, MA-RS models improve random outlier detection com-
396 pared with MA models. In every case, after the random outliers detected by the MA model
397 are removed, the RS model is able to find more spatially local random outliers and remove
398 them as well. Finally, the RS-MA model also improves upon the MA model alone in terms
399 of detecting random outliers but does not do quite as well as the MA-RS model. However,
400 this approach is worth considering since it can also detect the systematic outliers when the
401 RS model is applied first. When applying MA first followed by RS, the trend, including
402 any jumps, is removed from the residuals of the MA model, so no systematic errors would
403 then be detected by the RS model. Thus, the RS-MA approach can detect both systematic
404 outliers and some random outliers, and then the MA model applied to these residuals can
405 identify most of the remaining random outliers.

406 To further illustrate, Figure 8 shows the temporal plots of the systematic and random
407 outliers detected by RS-MA model for three monitoring stations. The modeling approach
408 is RS-MA with $\Delta = 3$ for both RS and MA modeling stages. Station 717 (left column)
409 contains 11 introduced random outliers, and RS-MA detects all of them, plus 4 additional
410 random outliers in the original ground deformation dataset. Station 1252 (middle column)
411 contains both introduced systematic outliers and introduced random outliers, and RS-MA
412 detects all systematic outliers, 10 of the 12 introduced random outliers, and one that does
413 not appear to be an outlier (bottom right corner). Station 1257 contains introduced random
414 outliers and systematic outliers that already exist in the ground deformation data. RS-MA
415 detects all systematic outliers and random outliers, plus one random outlier that already
416 exists in the data.

417 Figure 9 shows the spatial plots of the systematic and random outliers detected by RS-MA
418 model for four monitoring time points. Again, the modeling approach is RS-MA with $\Delta = 3$
419 for both RS and MA modeling stages. At time point 2011-12-29 02:24:00 (top left), the RS-
420 MA model correctly detects four introduced systematic outliers and one introduced random
421 outlier. At time point 2012-01-04 16:48:00 (top right), the RS-MA model correctly detects six
422 introduced systematic outliers, four introduced random outliers, and one outlier that exists
423 in the ground deformation data. At time point 2012-02-12 19:12:00 (bottom left), the RS-
424 MA model correctly detects 11 introduced systematic outliers and three introduced random
425 outlier, missed two introduced systematic outliers, and detects one outlier in the ground
426 deformation data. At time point 2012-03-13 16:48:00 (bottom right), the RS-MA model
427 correctly detects four introduced systematic outliers and two introduced random outliers,
428 missed two introduced systematic outliers and one introduced random outliers, but detects
429 one random outlier and one systematic outlier in the ground deformation data.

430 5 Discussion

431 In this work, we have developed a rapid spatial-temporal method for detecting systematic
432 and random outliers. For systematic outlier detection, we show that using robust param-
433 eter estimation and kriging prediction are extremely important to ensure good predictions
434 and thereby good outlier detection performance. By studying the properties of the ground
435 deformation data, we adopt anisotropic robust kriging models to account for the directional
436 variation and further improve the outlier detection. For random outlier detection, because
437 of the strong homogeneity in the temporal data at each station, exponential moving average
438 models successfully remove most of the random outliers, and a combination of temporal
439 models and spatial models improve the random outlier detection. Using robust spatial mod-
440 els first and then moving average models can remove both systematic and random outliers
441 in the ground deformation data.

442 The choice of the spatial model is important since a good choice will result in good
443 predictions. Some of the robust empirical semi-variograms (Genton, 1998) constructed in
444 our exploratory analysis suggested that a wave semi-variogram model may further improve
445 predictions, but the exponential model works well in practice. In addition, spatial-temporal
446 kriging in which a weighted average of not only the spatial neighbors but also the temporal
447 neighbors could also improve predictions in future work. However, the difficulties of fitting
448 spatial-temporal models for the ground deformation data are twofold. First, it is not trivial
449 to extend the robust kriging model by Künsch et al. (2011) to the spatial-temporal domain.
450 Second, fitting a robust spatial-temporal model and doing prediction using the leave-one-out
451 approach that we adopted here is time consuming, and therefore may be impractical for
452 online implementation. Regardless of how predictions are made, when outliers are present
453 in the dataset, comparing the predictions based on different model choices should be done
454 robustly through measures such as $SPI(\alpha)$.

455 The threshold, the value beyond which an observation is classified as an outlier, is also

456 a crucial choice. For the systematic outlier detection, the parametric outlier bounds are
457 better than nonparametric bounds, but for the random outlier detection, they are similar.
458 The value of α or Δ should be set after consultation with the subject-matter expert and
459 certainly after some visual assessment of the legitimacy of the observations that are flagged.
460 Finally, in processes that have the potential to evolve over time, a rolling window, such as the
461 one implemented here, allows the outlier detection to be updated dynamically with recent
462 information.

463 In this paper, we argue that spatial models are better for detecting systematic errors,
464 which in this application are likely to be malfunctioning instruments. Since this dataset
465 displays stronger temporal dependence, a purely temporal model, the exponential moving
466 average model, correctly detects most of the random outliers. Future research can be done
467 to investigate the relationship between the optimal models needed to detect random outliers
468 and the spatial-temporal variation. In our dataset, variation in space was stronger than
469 variability in time, but if the opposite were true, then the spatial model may be better for
470 detecting random outliers than the temporal model.

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536 Table 1. The systematic outlier detection results by using nonparametric outlier bounds
537 ($\alpha = 0.02, 0.03, 0.04$), and parametric outlier bounds ($\Delta = 4, 3, 2.5$). The modeling ap-
538 proaches are the non-robust kriging model (NR), the robust isotropic kriging model (ISO),
539 and the robust anisotropic kriging model (ANISO). A “D +” indicates observations that
540 were detected, and “D -” are observations that were not flagged.

Model		$\alpha = 0.02$		$\alpha = 0.03$		$\alpha = 0.04$	
		D +	D -	D +	D -	D +	D -
NR	Artificial	3433 (46%)	4013 (54%)	4937 (66%)	2509 (34%)	5955 (80%)	1491 (20%)
	Raw Data	3145	564459	4847	562757	7045	560559
ISO	Artificial	3497 (47%)	3949 (53%)	5127 (69%)	2319 (31%)	6222 (84%)	1224 (16%)
	Raw Data	3061	564543	4626	562978	6718	560886
ANISO	Artificial	3502 (47%)	3944 (53%)	5144 (69%)	2302 (31%)	6255 (84%)	1191 (16%)
	Raw Data	3025	564579	4557	563047	6605	560999

Model		$\Delta = 4$		$\Delta = 3$		$\Delta = 2.5$	
		D +	D -	D +	D -	D +	D -
NR	Artificial	2814 (38%)	4632 (62%)	5117 (69%)	2329 (31%)	6281 (84%)	1165 (16%)
	Raw Data	2041	565563	3435	564169	5136	562468
ISO	Artificial	3366 (45%)	4080 (55%)	5924 (80%)	1522 (20%)	6803 (91%)	643 (9%)
	Raw Data	2358	565246	3540	564064	4773	562831
ANISO	Artificial	3623 (49%)	3823 (51%)	6084 (82%)	1362 (18%)	6946 (93%)	500 (7%)
	Raw Data	2488	565116	3604	564000	4846	562758

543 Table 2. The random outlier detection results using nonparametric outlier bounds ($\alpha =$
544 0.01, 0.02, 0.04) and parametric outlier bounds ($\Delta = 4, 3, 2.5$). The modeling approaches
545 are the exponential moving average model (MA), the robust spatial kriging model (RS), the
546 exponential moving average model followed by the robust kriging model (MA-RS), and the
547 robust kriging model followed by the exponential moving average model (RS-MA). A “D +”
548 indicates observations that were detected, and “D -” are observations that were not flagged.

Model		$\alpha = 0.01$		$\alpha = 0.02$		$\alpha = 0.04$	
		D +	D -	D +	D -	D +	D -
MA	Artificial	2160 (68%)	1025 (32%)	2842 (89%)	343 (11%)	3074 (97%)	111 (3%)
	Raw Data	1252	570613	3946	567919	10329	561536
RS	Artificial	141 (4%)	3044 (96%)	396 (12%)	2789 (88%)	1143 (36%)	2042 (64%)
	Raw Data	3231	568634	6131	565734	11717	560148
MA-RS	Artificial	2858 (89%)	327 (11%)	3091 (97%)	94 (3%)	3147 (99%)	38 (1%)
	Raw Data	3736	568129	9851	562014	22039	549826
RS-MA	Artificial	2226 (70%)	959 (30%)	2810 (88%)	375 (12%)	3087 (97%)	98 (3%)
	Raw Data	4461	567404	9627	562238	22380	549485

Model		$\Delta = 4$		$\Delta = 3$		$\Delta = 2.5$	
		D +	D -	D +	D -	D +	D -
MA	Artificial	2055 (65%)	1130 (35%)	2646 (83%)	539 (17%)	2871 (90%)	314 (10%)
	Raw Data	1086	570779	2407	569458	3939	567926
RS	Artificial	172 (5%)	3013 (95%)	459 (14%)	2726 (86%)	739 (23%)	2446 (77%)
	Raw Data	5939	565926	9229	562636	11053	560812
MA-RS	Artificial	2849 (89%)	336 (11%)	3072 (96%)	113 (4%)	3110 (98%)	75 (2%)
	Raw Data	3430	568435	8329	563536	13881	557984
RS-MA	Artificial	2299 (72%)	886 (28%)	2841 (89%)	344 (11%)	3024 (95%)	161 (5%)
	Raw Data	7183	564682	12360	559505	16638	555227

549

550

Figure 1: Map of the measurement stations along with the final locations of the four tunnels.

Figure 2: On top is an example of a time series of ATMS observations at a station where a systematic shift occurs prior to the first tunnel being bored. On bottom is an example wherein some random errors occur after all tunnels have been bored.

Figure 3: Comparison of omni-directional (left) and directional (right) semi-variogram for ground deformation at time 2012-03-09 00:00:00.

Figure 4: The box plots of the SPI(0.05) for ground deformation predictions at all time points using the non-robust kriging model (left), the robust isotropic kriging model (middle), and the robust anisotropic model (right). The robust anisotropic model produces the highest median SPI (0.52), followed by the robust isotropic model (0.44). The non-robust kriging model produces the worst SPI with a median of -0.01 .

Figure 5: The observed and predicted ground deformation using the leave-one-out approach for all stations at time point 2012-04-04 14:24:00 (top row) and time point 2011-12-13 19:12:00 (bottom row), by using the non-robust kriging model (left column), the robust isotropic kriging model (middle column) and the robust anisotropic model (right column). The prediction using the non-robust kriging model is greatly affected by the existence of outliers, but predictions are much better using robust kriging models.

Figure 6: Detected systematic outliers (red dots) for Station 707 (left) and its nearest Station 706 by using non-robust spatial kriging models (middle) and robust spatial kriging models (right). Both non-robust and robust kriging models correctly detect the systematic outliers for Station 707, but the non-robust kriging model identifies many observations at Station 706 that do appear unusual. The robust kriging model's predictions identify fewer outliers at Station 706.

Figure 7: The nonparametric (left column) and parametric (right column) outlier bounds for the robust anisotropic kriging (RS) model (top row) and exponential moving average (MA) model (bottom row). We set $\alpha = 0.02$ for both nonparametric bounds and $\Delta = 3$ for both parametric bounds.

Figure 8: Time series plots of ground deformation data at three monitoring stations with introduced systematic outliers (blue line), introduced random outliers (red dots), detected systematic outliers (blue star), and detected random outliers (red star).

Figure 9: The spatial plots of ground deformation (mm) at four monitoring time points with introduced systematic outliers (blue circle), introduced random outliers (red circle), detected systematic outliers (blue triangle), and detected random outliers (red triangle).